

ERROR-CORRECTING GENERALIZED FINITE SET CODE BASED ON GENERALIZED SPHERES

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Abstract. Based on the concept of a generalized sphere introduced in the author's early works, this article introduces the concept of an abstract symmetric channel with a given set of symbols for transmitting information and for such a channel the concept of a generalized error-correcting code is introduced. A theorem on the number of such abstract symmetric channels is formulated. The concept of a perfect generalized error-correcting code is also introduced. A simple example of a generalized error-correcting code is given.

Keywords: correction code, sphere, sphere, generalized sphere, symmetric communication channel, discrete metric space, finite sets, combinatorics, discrete sets.

Annotatsiya. Muallifning dastlabki ishlarida kiritilgan umumlashtirilgan shar kontseptsiyasiga asosanib, ushbu maqolada ma'lumotni uzatish uchun berilgan belgilar to'plamiga ega abstrakt simmetrik kanal tushunchasi va bunday kanal uchun umumlashtirilgan xatolarni tuzatish kodi tushunchasi kiritiladi. Bunday abstrakt simmetrik kanallar soni haqida teorema keltiriladi. Mukammal umumlashtirilgan xatolarni tuzatuvchi kod tushunchasi ham kiritilgan. Umumlashtirilgan xatolarni tuzatish kodining oddiy misoli keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tuzatish kodi, shar, sfera, umumlashtirilgan shar, simmetrik aloqa kanali, diskret metrik fazo, chekli to'plamlar, kombinatorika, diskret to'plamlar.

Аннотация. На основе введенного в ранних работах автора понятия обобщенного шара в данной статье вводится понятие абстрактного симметричного канала с заданным множеством символов для передачи информации и для такого канала вводится понятие обобщенного кода, исправляющего ошибки. Сформулирована теорема о числе таких абстрактных симметричных каналов. Вводится также понятие совершенного обобщенного кода, исправляющего ошибки. Приводится простейший пример обобщенного кода, исправляющего ошибки.

Ключевые слова: Корректирующий код, шар, сфера, обобщенный шар, симметричный канал связи, дискретное метрическое пространство, конечные множества, комбинаторика, дискретные множества.

As is known [1], the theory of correcting codes (or the theory of error-correcting codes) arose as a practical need for the reliable transmission of information over various real communication channels. Such channels include not only such traditional, classical communication channels as telephone, telegram, radio communications, etc., but also modern local and global networks (Internet). And when it comes to storing information, the real channel for transmitting information is the time during which it is necessary to safely store information - to safely transmit information from one point in time to another. To transmit information over all such real channels, the transmitted information is first translated into a sequence of symbols that can be transmitted over a given channel - this process is called encoding, and the sequence of channel symbols into which the transmitted (initial) information is translated is called a code. In all real information transmission channels, there is noise, as a result of which the code transmitted at the beginning of the channel is distorted and at the end of the channel, generally

speaking, a different sequence of symbols is obtained, different from the transmitted code. The process of reconstructing the sent code from this received sequence of characters is called decoding. For decoding to be possible and successful, encoding must be carried out with a special error-resistant code - these are the codes that are called error-correcting codes. There are also codes that only detect errors without the possibility of correction - in such cases, the task of transmitting information is solved by retransmission, i.e. Having detected an error during reception, the sending side is informed about this and asked to repeat the transmission. This, of course, increases the overhead of transmitting and receiving information over the communication channel.

The theory of error-correcting codes deals, in particular, with the construction of efficient codes in which each codeword (i.e., a sequence of transmitted symbols) serves as the center of a sphere with a certain radius. Since the radius is generally defined within a metric space, such codes consist of points (centers of spheres with a given radius) in a metric space. These metric spaces are also linear spaces over corresponding finite fields. Leveraging a well-developed mathematical framework, the theory of error-correcting codes rapidly evolved, paying special attention to linear codes capable of correcting errors. Many important properties of error-correcting codes have been studied, and intriguing problems were formulated in a scientific dissertation [2], which has inspired—and continues to inspire—some researchers [3], [4]. However, some of these authors fail to acknowledge the original source of these brilliant ideas in their subsequent publications.

Although the theory of error-correcting codes primarily focuses on studying codes for channels where the set of transmitted sequences (i.e., codewords) forms a linear metric space, real-world channel modeling may reveal that such sets are neither metric spaces nor linear spaces. Here, we focus on modeling such channels and defining error-correcting codes suitable for them.

Let us consider an abstract channel through which elements from a set M can be transmitted at one end and received at the other. If all possible transmitted elements belong to the set A , and all possible received elements belong to the set B , then by combining these two sets, we obtain the set M , i.e., $M = A \cup B$. The set M is referred to as the set of symbols (or the set of possibilities) of the given abstract channel.

Suppose that an element $\alpha \in M$, transmitted at one end, may, due to distortions in the channel, be received as any element from a subset of M . Let this subset be denoted as $\varphi(\alpha)$. It is clear that the subset $\varphi(\alpha)$ (whether empty or non-empty) exists for each $\alpha \in M$. Thus, a mapping $\varphi: M \rightarrow 2^M$ arises. If this mapping is a generalized sphere [5], the corresponding abstract channel is called symmetric. The symmetry of the channel essentially means that if, due to distortions, the symbol α transmitted through the channel can be received as the symbol β , then the symbol β , if transmitted, can also be received as α . Thus, for each symmetric abstract channel with the set of symbols M , there is a corresponding generalized sphere $\varphi: M \rightarrow 2^M$, and conversely, for each generalized sphere $\varphi: M \rightarrow 2^M$, there is a corresponding symmetric abstract channel. In these new terms, Theorem 1 from [5] can be reformulated as follows:

Theorem. The number of symmetric abstract channels with a finite set of symbols M , consisting of m elements, is equal to $2^{m(m+1)/2}$.

We observe that a specific symmetric abstract channel, by definition, implies the existence of its own set of symbols (its own set of possibilities) and its corresponding generalized sphere.

Now, let us consider a symmetric abstract channel with a finite set of symbols M and its corresponding generalized sphere $\varphi: M \rightarrow 2^M$.

Definition 1. A subset $C \subset M$ is called a generalized error-correcting code if, for any $\alpha \in C$ and $\beta \in C$, $\alpha \neq \beta$, the condition $\varphi(\alpha) \cap \varphi(\beta) = \emptyset$ holds (i.e., the generalized spheres centered at points α and β do not overlap). The number of elements in the subset $C \subset M$ is referred to as the size of the generalized code C .

Definition 2. A generalized error-correcting code $C \subset M$ is called a perfect generalized error-correcting code if the union of all $\varphi(\alpha)$, where $\alpha \in C$, equals the set M .

The main problem of error-correcting code theory can now be generalized for generalized error-correcting codes as follows:

For a given abstract symmetric channel with a finite set of symbols M and its corresponding generalized sphere $\varphi: M \rightarrow 2^M$, find the generalized error-correcting code with the maximum size.

Example. Let $M = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ be the set of channel symbols, and let the generalized sphere for this set be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(1) &= \{1, 2, 3\}, & \varphi(2) &= \{2, 1, 4, 5, 6\}, & \varphi(3) &= \{3, 1, 4, 5, 6\}, \\ \varphi(4) &= \{4, 2, 3, 7\}, & \varphi(5) &= \{5, 2, 3, 7\}, & \varphi(6) &= \{6, 2, 3, 7\}, & \varphi(7) &= \{7, 4, 5, 6\}. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see that the subset $C = \{1, 7\} \subset M$ is a generalized error-correcting code. Clearly, $|C| = 2$, i.e., the size of this generalized code is 2. Since the generalized spheres $\varphi(1)$ and $\varphi(7)$, centered at the code points, do not overlap ($\varphi(1) \cap \varphi(7) = \emptyset$), and their union $\varphi(1) \cup \varphi(7) = M$, this generalized code is also a perfect generalized error-correcting code.

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